

Analysis of Potential Land Support for Beef Cattle Development in the Integrated Area of Gorontalo Province

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Abstract

This study aims to identify and analyze the carrying capacity of the land available for the development of beef cattle farms. The method in this research is a survey method using a systems approach. The data analysis method used is descriptive analysis. Site selection is done by purposive sampling method, with the consideration that this region is one of the integrated agricultural areas where one of the leading commodities is beef cattle. Data collected include secondary data related to research topics are derived from: a) BPS Regency Bone Bolango, b) the Department of Agriculture and Livestock District Bone Bolango. The data is then processed and analyzed through i calculation of Index Carrying Capacity of land and capacity increase in beef cattle population (KPPSP). Agricultural land in Bone regency Bolango has the potential to produce HMT 42788.72 ha. The land is derived from secondary forests, upland, wetland, and grazing land. While food plants that can produce agricultural waste that can be used as animal feed for 88. 625, 55 tons of BK/year. This agricultural waste comes from corn, rice, peanuts, soybean, sweet potatoes and cassava. The results of the analysis show that the capacity of cattle in Bone Bolango Regency has a carrying capacity index value of 8.21 with the IDD category safe for all districts. Based on carrying capacity of the dry ingredients, District of Bone Bolango able to accommodate as many cattle ST 144,016.73 from existing livestock population of 23 607 ST, with a capacity of Livestock Population Increased by 120 410 ST. Whereas in the integrated farming area based on the carrying capacity of dry material is able to accommodate beef cattle as many as 9,338 ST of the existing livestock population of 2,021 ST, with an Increase in Livestock Population Capacity of 7,317 ST, assuming that all food crop waste is used as animal feed, so the area This has a great opportunity for the development of beef cattle in the future.

Keywords: beef cattle, livestock units, carrying capacity index. KPPSP

Introduction

Livestock development as an integral part in the development of the agricultural sector plays a role in the supply of animal protein, employment, poverty alleviation and regional potential development. Along with increasing public knowledge and income, the demand for food from animal protein sources is also experiencing an increase, especially for poultry products and beef cattle. For this reason, the development of the livestock sub-sector needs special attention while paying attention to the preservation of existing resources and the environment. This is because activities in the livestock sub-sector have an important role in increasing farmer's income, economic equality and employment opportunities, as well as improvements in community nutrition. This goal can be achieved through increasing population, production and livestock productivity. Animal husbandry development strategies to achieve optimal results require careful and precise planning so that the area used for animal husbandry development activities does not compete with other activities and does not interfere with the farm itself and the surrounding environment. For this reason, a specific arrangement of livestock zones is needed, arranged based on the potential land needed for raising

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livestock, access to marketing areas and facilities and infrastructure that support businesses in the livestock sector. Thus it is expected that activities in the field of animal husbandry can run safely and smoothly and be able to produce optimal production in terms of quality and quantity.

Bone Bolango District as one of the areas in the province of Gorontalo has considerable potential for the development of beef cattle farms this case due to which the region has a carrying capacity of the availability of fodder in the form of forage and waste abundant of agriculture and location of a strategic region because it borders the centre of the provincial capital city, Gorontalo City as the largest consumer of meat products from livestock, especially beef. Based on BPS data (2016), Bone Bolango Regency has an area of 198,458 ha, where most of the area island that has the potential as a provider of fodder feed. The area covers 33,185 ha (16.72%) as agricultural land (rice fields, tegal / gardens and fields / Huma), 140,429.39 ha (70.76%) as forest (state forest and community forest), and 11.84% is used as grazing land and beef cattle population in 2016 amounted to 36,512 3 Cor.

Based on the potential possessed, Bone Bolango Regency is one of the areas that has been determined by the Provincial Government based on Governor Decree Number 96/20 / III / 2015 as the location of Integrated Agricultural Area Development based on intercropping plants and livestock based on the potential of integrated agricultural areas, namely land conditions , availability of water sources, Human Resources, location accessibility and production facilities. Besides the integrated farming pattern is a pattern that integrates several business units that are managed in an integrated, ecologically oriented manner to obtain an increase in economic value, a high level of efficiency and productivity.

Beef cattle farms have been designated as one of the leading regional commodities by the government of Bone Bolango Regency in addition to poultry and other commodities. This policy has been strongly responded by the community based on facts on the ground, among others a) market opportunities that are still quite open where the market demand for beef cattle commodities is quite high, b) the potential and carrying capacity of land as a source of forage is available to support the development of cattle farming beef cattle, c) the suitability of agro-climate conditions, d) the culture of the community and the workforce in this area is very supportive of the development of beef cattle farming, e) the high level of local government support for beef cattle farming (BPS, 2016). But to develop the cattle population beef in a region requires a knowledge of the potential of the region, in particular, the availability of forage in supporting livestock populations will be developed and how much potential the region can accommodate ruminants. Research has been conducted to determine the potential of feed resources in Bone Bolango Regency in supporting the development of beef cattle.

Novelty (novelty) in this study consists of two things, namely:

(1) The novelty of the method is a comprehensive and participatory combination of several analytical methods to assess the potential carrying capacity of beef cattle development land in a sustainable integrated farming area in Bone Bolango Regency

(2) The novelty of the research results is to develop integrated agricultural development based on beef cattle farms in terms of natural resource potential and to know the influential future factors, as well as the sustainability strategy of developing integrated farming areas based on beef cattle farms in Bone Bolango Regency.

Research methods

The method used in the study is a survey method using a systems approach. The study began by identifying and analyzing the land available for the development of beef cattle breeding areas. The results of this analysis become one source to provide information about the capacity of beef cattle population increase through the analysis of the carrying capacity of the land for beef cattle development. The data used in this study are secondary in the form of beef cattle population, a land-use area, area of food crops, plantations and

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grazing land and also conduct field verification. The data is sourced from Bone Bolango District Statistics Data 2017, Bone Bolang District Agriculture and Animal Husbandry Office o.

Data analysis method

The data analysis method used in this study was carried out in the following stages:

Calculation of Land Support Capacity Suitable for Beef Cattle Development.

Carrying capacity of fodder forage is the ability of an area to produce fodder in the form of forage that can be produced for the needs of beef cattle populations in fresh or dried form, without going through special processing and it is assumed to be used only for beef cattle. Forage several capacity is calculated based on the production of dry matter (BK) to the needs of one unit of livestock (1 ST) beef cattle in one year where the need for dry matter is 6.25 kg/day or 2.28 tons/year (NCR, 1984), for cows with a live weight of up to 500 kg. For cattle in Indonesia in general, every 1 ST has a live weight range of 200-250 kg. So the minimum feed / dry material requirement for 1 ST for one year can vary depending on the live weight of the cow. The minimum feed requirement of ruminants per animal unit (1 ST) is calculated according to Sumanto and Juarini (2006) as follows:

$$K = 2.5\% \times 50\% \times 365 \times 250 \text{ Kg} = 1.14 \text{ tons of BKC} / \text{year} / \text{ST}$$

Information

K = Minimum feed requirement for 1 ST in tons of digested dry matter for one year

2.5% = Minimum requirement for the amount of feed forage (dry matter) to body weight.

50% = Average value of digestibility of various types of plants

The availability of agricultural food waste is calculated based on Muller's formula (1974), as follows:

- a. Rice Straw = (2.5 x land area x 0.70) BK BK / year
- b. Corn Straw = (6.0 x land area x 0.75) BK BK / year
- c. Peanut Soybeans = (2.5 x land area x 0.60) tons of BK / year
- d. Peanut Straw = (2.5 x land area x 0.60) BK BK / year
- e. Sweet Potato Straw = (1.5 x land area x 0.80) tons of BK / year
- f. Cassava = (1.0 x land area x 0.30) tons of BK / year

The results of the calculation of dry matter production are then used to obtain the carrying capacity of forage feed using the following equation (Haryanto, *et al.* 2002)

Dry Material Production (KG)

Carrying Capacity (ST) =

Dry Needs of Adult Cow (KG / ST)

Livestock Unit (ST) is a unit for the population of ruminant animals obtained from the population multiplied by a conversion factor. . The calculation of the number of cattle population based on the age of livestock used the conversion value of young, young and adult livestock to the population of each ruminant livestock. The percentage values used are shown in Table 1. To calculate the number of ruminant livestock units (ST) for each type of livestock, the livestock population is calculated based on population structure (tail) multiplied by the standard value of livestock units.

Table 1. Livestock population structure and livestock unit standards according to age and type of livestock

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Livestock Unit Standards (ST)

Type of livestock	Son	Young	Adult
Cow	0.25	0.60	1,00
Horse	0.25	0.60	1,00
Buffalo	0.29	0.69	1.15
Goat	0.04	0.08	.16
Sheep	0.04	0.07	0.14

Sources: Krisnan and Ginting, 2011

Capacity to increase beef cattle population (KPPSP)

Carrying capacity is the ability to accommodate livestock per unit area to provide optimum results or the capacity of forage feed needs which are calculated based on livestock units (Winarto, 2010). The value of increasing beef cattle capacity is calculated as the difference between the carrying capacity of food crop waste and the number of beef cattle population-based on livestock units (ST). The KPPSP percentage value is calculated using the formula:

Result and Discussion

1. Potential for Fee- in Bone Bolango Regency

Agricultural Land besides Meadows in Producing Forages

In addition to pasture, other pasture lands such as rice fields, plantations, forests and dry fields contribute to forages that are different in number from each other. In the following table can be seen the contribution of agricultural land in addition to pasture in Bone Bolango Regency.

Information: LP (Pastoral Land), LS (Wetland), LK (Dry land, consisting of fields, gardens, fields, roadsides), LH (secondary forest land) . From Table 2 above it appears that agricultural lands in Bone Bolango Regency have been used, but still have the potential to produce forages 42,788.72 Ha. The land is derived from secondary forests with a total contribution of 28324.01 hectares, dryland total contributions amounted to 13008.06 ha, the total contribution of wetland area of 1.200.59 ha, and grazing land with contributions totalling an area of 238.05 hectares. This is in accordance with the opinion of Makka (2004) in the area of animal husbandry development that integrates with other sub-sectors, the development of ruminant livestock such as large ruminants such as cattle can utilize by-product (waste and agricultural products) available from activities in other subsectors such as food crops, horticultural and estate crops , as well as the needs and fisheries as animal feed.

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Table 2 . Contribution of Agricultural Land Besides Meadows in Producing Forages

No	sub-district	Production of Dried Material (tonnes BK) Forage Grass				Total (Tons)
		LP	LS	LK	LH	
1	Tapa	3.45	14.87	586.02	1,838,5	2,442.88
2	North Bulango	13,80	19.91	1,095.03	2,594.1	3,722.81
3	South Bulango	3.45	181,19	537.05	-	721.69
4	East Bulango	13,80	119.51	625.99	-	759.30
5	Bulango Ulu	6.90	41.01	621.25	3,061,7	3,730.91
6	Kabila	13,80	301.17	802.07	-	1,117.05
7	Botupingge	-	-	212.34	840,5	1,052.84
8	Tilongkabila	13,80	391.74	2,086.23	2,168,5	4,660.24
9	Suwawa	6.90	77.99	1112.91	1,472.3	2,670.12
10	South Suwawa	69.00	-	782.57	3,178,1	4,029.71
11	East Suwawa	27.60	-	525.16	4,426,1	4,978.81
12	Central Suwawa	13,80	-	293.94	5,439,8	5,747,54
13	Pinogu	13,80	53.21	440.49	-	507.50
14	Bone Beach	6.90	-	551.85	-	558,75
15	Kabila Bone	6.90	-	500.86	3,322,4	3,830.16
16	Bone Raya	6.90	-	341.00	-	347.90
17	Bone	13,80	-	1,484.86	-	1,498.66
18	Bulawa	3.45	-	408.42	-	411.87
total		238.05	1,200,59	13,008.06	28,342.01	42,788.72

Source: Processed data (2018)

The area of land that has the potential to produce forages, both originating from pasture land and those originating from other agricultural lands, can be known the total potential of land in Bone Bolango Regency to produce forages.

Food Crop Agricultural Land in Producing Straw Waste

Food crops such as rice, corn, soybean, cassava and sweet potato are potential sources of animal feed besides grass. Food crop waste is in the form of straw or part of leaves and stems from plants after the harvest is taken. Soybean leaves, peanuts, cassava and sweet potato leaves in addition to fibre feed are also a source of protein feed for ruminants. To support the production of lactating dairy cows in feed, more concentrate must be added. Rice straw and corn straw can be used as a source of fibre feed. The feed is needed for dairy cows, especially to improve milk fat content.

The potential of food crop straw is estimated from the harvested area of each agricultural crop commodity. The potential of feed origin of fibre presented in Table 3 already takes into account the portion or proportion of plants that can be utilized by livestock, especially ruminants. For more details can be seen in the following table.

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Table 3 . Agriculture Land In Generate Waste Straw

No	sub-district	Production of Dry Material (tonnes BK) Food Crop Waste						Total
		JP	JJ	JKK	JKT	JUJ	JUK	
1	Tapa	183,75	4,356.00	-	12.0	-	-	4,551.75
2	North Bulango	246.05	6,273.00	-	-	-	-	6,519.05
3	South Bulango	2,239.30	585.00	-	-	-	-	2,824.30
4	East Bulango	1,477.00	4,140.00	-	6.0	-	2.40	5625.40
5	Bulango Ulu	506.80	7,191.00	-	-	-	-	7,697.80
6	Kabila	3,722.25	1,404.00	-	-	-	-	5,126,25
7	Botupingge	-	1,773.00	-	-	-	-	1,773.00
8	Tilongkabila	4,841,55	6,885.00	-	48.0	21.60	7.80	11,803.95
9	Suwawa	963.90	4,887.00	-	-	-	-	5850.90
10	South Suwawa	-	8,334.00	34.50	-	-	-	8,368.50
11	East Suwawa	-	4,725.00	-	-	-	-	4,725.00
12	Central Suwawa	-	3,357.00	-	-	-	-	3,357.00
13	Pinogu	657.65	144.00	-	-	-	-	801.65
14	Bone Beach	-	5,445.00	-	-	-	-	5,445.00
15	Kabila Bone	-	3,429.00	-	-	-	-	3,429.00
16	Bone Raya	-	1,224.00	-	60.0	-	-	1,284.00
17	Bone	-	6,579.00	-	-	-	-	6,579.00
18	Bulawa	-	2,853.00	-	12.0	-	-	2,865.00
total		14,838.25	73,584.00	34.50	138.00	21.60	10,20	88,626,55

Source: Processed data (2018)

Captions: JP (Rice Straw), JJ (Corn Straw), JKK (Soy Bean Straw), JKT (Peanut Straw), JUJ (Sweet Potato Straw), PUK (Cassava Shoots)

Captions: JP (Rice Straw), JJ (Corn Straw), JKK (Soy Bean Straw), JKT (Peanut Straw), JUJ (Sweet Potato Straw), PUK (Cassava Shoots)

From Table 3 above it is known that existing food crops can produce agricultural waste that can be used as animal feed for 88 . 625 , 55 tons of BK / year. This agricultural waste comes from corn with a total waste production of 73 . 584.00 tons BK / year, Paddy with a total waste production of 14 . 833 , 25 tons of BK / year, and peanuts, soybean sweet potato and cassava with a total waste production of 204 , 30 tons of BK / year.

Some sub-districts have higher dry matter crop production than other regions, such as Tilongkabila sub-district 11,803.95 (13.32%), South Suwawa 8,368.50 (9.44%), Bulango Ulu 7,697.80 (8, 69%) and Bone 6,579.00 (7.42%), North Bulango 6,519.05 (7.36%). Around 50% of food crop waste production in Bone Bolango Regency is found in these five sub-districts, including one of the Districts which is an integrated agricultural area. The high production of food crop waste in the region is influenced by the area of corn

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harvesting area so that it produces more tall straw, and ultimately it affects the high total production of dry matter food crop waste

Based on the production of food crop waste that has been described above, the facts can be stated as follows a). Corn straw waste is more evenly distributed in all districts in Bone Bolango Regency and is the highest production compared to other types of plant waste. b). Food crop waste production is strongly influenced by the size of the planted area of the cash crop commodity in each district. The wider the planting area of a food commodity, the more food crop waste production is produced. c). Some sub-districts have high production in certain types of food crop waste that can be a sign of the ability and availability of potential waste in each region. d). The development of livestock, especially cattle in utilizing food crop waste as cattle, duly pays attention to the availability of waste production in accordance with specifications and locality (Syamsu , 2006).

In the approach of farming as a system, there are at least two things that need attention, first is the structure and the system itself. In its function as a component of farming, livestock will interact with other commodity lands cultivated, and with farmers as farm managers (Siregar et al, 1981).

Animal feed from plants can be in the form of residues and by-products of agro-industry that can be used for ruminants and non-ruminants including: (1) straw (rice and corn), (2) sugarcane shoots, (3) grains (peanuts and coffee), (4) tubers (yams and sweet potatoes), (5) oil seed meal (palm oil, cotton, copra), (6) bran, and (7) baggase (Makka, 2004).

1. Carrying Capacity of Regions Based on Potential Feeds for Beef Cattle Development in Bone Bolango Regency

The carrying capacity of forage and food crop waste is the ability of an area to produce or provide food in the form of forage and food crop waste that can accommodate a number of ruminant livestock populations in this case beef cattle. Carrying capacity of forage and crop waste as a source of cattle feed in Bone Bolango Regency based on dry matter is presented in Table 4 .

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Table 4 . Regional Support Capacity for the Development of Cattle Based on Potential of Origin of Forage and Agricultural Waste

No	sub-district	Cow Population (ST)	Prod. BK (Tons of BK)	DD (ST)	IDD	Category	KPPSP
1	Tapa	752	6,994.63	7,665.34	10,19	Secure	6,913
2	North Bulango	1,822	10,241.86	11,223.96	6.16	Secure	9,402
3	South Bulango	1,793	3,545.99	3,886.02	2.17	Secure	2,093
4	East Bulango	937	6,384.70	6996.93	7.47	Secure	6,060
5	Bulango Ulu	1,058	11,428.71	12524.61	11.83	Secure	11,666
6	Kabila	2015	6,243.30	6,841.97	3.40	Secure	4,827
7	Botupingge	1,040	2,825.84	3096.81	2.98	Secure	2,056
8	Tilongkabila	5,615	16,464.19	18,042.94	3.21	Secure	12,428
9	Suwawa	2,021	8,521.02	9,338.10	4.62	Secure	7,317
10	South Suwawa	615	12,398.21	13,587.08	22.09	Secure	12,972
11	East Suwawa	1,300	9,703.81	10344.32	8.18	Secure	9,335
12	Central Suwawa	434	9,104.54	9,977.58	22.98	Secure	9,543
13	Pinogu	409	1,309.15	1,434.69	3.51	Secure	1,026
14	Bone Beach	1,257	6,003.75	6,579.45	5.23	Secure	5,322
15	Kabila Bone	923	7,259.16	7,955.24	8.62	Secure	7,032
16	Bone Raya	428	1,631.90	1,788.38	4.18	Secure	1,360
17	Bone	597	8077.66	8,852.23	14.84	Secure	8,256
18	Bulawa	591	3,276.87	3,591.09	6.08	Secure	3,000
total		23,607	1.31,415	144,016.73	8.21		120,410

Source: Processed data (2018).

Data Table 4 shows that the potential for feed-in Bone Bolango District based on the carrying capacity of dry material is able to accommodate beef cattle as much as 144,016.73 ST, and all areas included in the IDD category are safe and areas that are still open for the development of beef cattle are areas that have power support the highest feed. Districts that have great opportunities for the development of beef cattle are Suwawa Selatan (12,975 ST), Tilongkabila (12,428 ST), Bulango Ulu (11,466 ST), North Bulango (9,042 ST), Central Suwawa (9,543 ST), East Suwawa (11,428 ST) 9,335 ST), Bone (8,256 ST), Suwawa (7,317 ST), Kabila Bone (7,032 ST). East Bulango (6,060 ST). From these data it appears that Suwawa Subdistrict is an area designated as an integrated agricultural development area that still has a great opportunity for future development of beef cattle assuming that if all feed originating from food crop waste is used as beef cattle feed, so that it will have an impact on sustainable development integrated farming area based on beef cattle farms which is one of the government programs in the field of animal husbandry.

Conclusion

In terms of quantity and quality, the capacity of cattle in Bone Bolango Regency exceeds the existing livestock population. This means that the available feed ingredients from agricultural waste and forage can exceed the population of cattle which have a carrying capacity index of 8.21 with the IDD category safe for

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all districts. Potential feed-in Bone Bolango Regency based on the carrying capacity of dry material can accommodate beef cattle as much as 144,016.73 ST of the existing livestock population of 23,607 ST, with an Increase in Livestock Population Capacity of 120,410 ST. Whereas in integrated farming areas, especially based on the carrying capacity of dry matter is able to accommodate beef cattle as many as 9,338 ST from the existing livestock population of 2,021 ST, with an Increase in Livestock Population Capacity of 7,317 ST, assuming if all food crop waste is used as animal feed, so This area has great opportunities for the development of beef cattle in the future.

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